

SPATIAL DESIGN FOR THE ENERGY TRANSITION

Exploring Tools and Approaches in Consolidated Urban Contexts

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Abstract

The space neutrality of eco-modernist energy policies contrasts the transition in many consolidated urban areas, in which “just technofix” transformations are not always feasible in historical, dense, fragmented and car-oriented urban patterns. What is lacking -and crucially needed- is understanding and developing design solutions that cross the scales from deepening the attention to existing configuration and living community. The ongoing research PEDFORALL is trying to interpret this challenge starting from a specific urban context -the neighborhood of Ostiense in Rome- exploring and testing possible design solutions for a place-based energy transition. Integrating diverse energy transition paradigms -as the energy sufficiency- the contribution builds a theoretical framework collecting and conceptualising design references in three main design strategies. The same strategies are tested then in the case study, raising first questions, limits and potentials of this application. The paper mainly suggests a spatial approach to energy transition, overcoming a mere idea of technological transformation to caring for the design of space (both domestic and urban) and for the bodies that inhabit it.

Keywords

energy sufficiency;
energy behaviours;
bioclimatic;
embedded energy;
Positive Energy
District

Energy Transition for No People and No Space: The Case of Rome

Urban environments consume vast amounts of the world's primary energy, not only for large-scale processes, but also to support everyday activities mediated by artificial lighting, transportation, climate control, and household appliances (Smil, 2021; Rahm, 2023a). All these uses are known but little visible, escaping from an awareness of consumption and contributing to a growing and “impact-blind” demand for energy. This dynamic, coupled with the evidence of exhaustibility and geopolitical instability of fossil sources, has fuelled an unprecedented global energy crisis (IEA, 2022). What is worrying is no longer the economic turbulence of the energy market but also the socio-spatial repercussions. The massive use of fossil fuels has reached levels of global climate disruption with evident and dramatic effects in hotspots like the Mediterranean countries (IPCC, 2022). Here, rising temperatures and Urban Heat Islands (UHI) affect vulnerable people (not only physically but also economically) and force extensive use of electrical appliances -such as air conditioners- generating evident and uncontrollable short circuits (Roesler, 2022). Furthermore, the persistence of the energy crisis is leading to supply shortages and a surge in energy prices (IEA, 2022), making Southern

Europe an "energy social hotspot" with a consistent number of people lacking adequate access to energy¹ and fuelling the phenomenon of energy poverty.

To address the energy crisis, the EU has shaped Community policies focused on an economy sensitive to technological development and environmental protection. The vision behind these policies follows the principles of the eco-modernist paradigm, thus the restructuring of the energy system for a sustainable metabolism starting from the economic and productive sectors (Asafu-Adjaye et al., 2015) and with appropriate "green" technologies promoted by incentives (Puttilli, 2014). The generous system of incentives has boosted the short-term implementation of new technologies, such as renewable energy plants (Frolova et al., 2019, Puttilli, 2014), and the technological efficiency of buildings and mobility systems that led to a wide urban retrofitting.² This acceleration represented a techno-economic success but, on the other hand, raised significant concerns on the socio-spatial dimension. First, the rapid and sprawled construction of new plants led to an accidental transformation of the landscape (Bridge, 2018; Frolova et al., 2019), where the space is considered just "a support" or a site "to be developed" for a maximum economic profit or technological functionalism (D'Angelo, 2023; Carrosio and Magnani, 2022). Second, the tax credit regulatory framework for efficiency does not contemplate specific spatial conditions (e.g. age, materials, heritage of buildings) or social conditions (e.g. ownership and economic status of dwellers) affecting the feasibility of interventions in existing buildings, specific climate conditions and different social groups. Third, the standardisation of some planning tools (e.g. Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan-SECAP), which are characterised by excessive expression of quantity, vague objectives, and lack of spatialised representation, completely affects the application in real contexts (De Pascali and Bagaini, 2018). More recently, models of Positive Energy District (PED)³ seem to propose innovative contextual approaches.⁴ A PED theoretically plans the energy transition at the neighbourhood scale to produce net-zero emissions and a local surplus of REN production (Gollner et al., 2020). The model, however, seems applicable today only in contexts governed by strong energy policies, with appropriate regulatory framework and with the availability of public-private investment capital (Bossi et al. 2020), all elements often weak

¹ For more details see the briefing of the European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS) edited by Agnieszka Widuto in September 2023. Link available at [www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2022/733583/EPRS_BRI\(2022\)733583_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2022/733583/EPRS_BRI(2022)733583_EN.pdf) (November 2023).

² A paradigmatic case is the Italian "Superbonus 110%" launched in 2020, a tax credit tool with a huge economic facilitation that led many buildings free intervention by deducting the expenses with the Tax Return, transferring credit to suppliers' banks or financial and insurance institutions, or with the discount on the invoice.

³ PED are actions foreseen in the European Strategic Energy Technology Plan for establish one hundred sustainable energy districts by 2030. For more details, see the SET-Plan Action n. 3.2, Implementation Plan, 2018. Link available at https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/setplan_smartcities_implementationplan-2.pdf (September 2024).

⁴ For example, the local scale of PED facilitates the involvement of people and local stakeholders and provides the integration of different energy systems with the territorial one, generating an idea of multioperability. In addition, the integration between systems and forms of government ensures greater context-relatedness.

or not present in consolidated urban patterns (and communities), even less in historical cities and Southern European countries (Bossi et al. 2020).

The three dynamics described underline how spatially neutral interpretations of the energy policies do not favour any social, cultural or economic group and do not consider the specificities of a local context. This neutrality led to a wider “space blindness” intended as the inability to design and plan considering the real spatial dynamics, a condition that inevitably produces conflicts, new pressures on resources, layers of injustice and inertia to energy transition programs (D’Angelo, 2023). A paradigmatic example of the cause-and-effect of this space blindness is the city of Rome, case study of this contribution. In the city, large parts of the buildings were built before or out of any energy regulations, often as a result of speculative and unauthorised processes (Insolera, 2011). These starting conditions have obstructed the implementation or renovation of technical services -such as the electric distribution grid- while the widespread and numerous presences of low-energy performance buildings still requires difficult mediation processes between ownership, regulation and financial systems. The spatial neutrality of local planning tools, such as the *Piano Quadro per la Transizione di Roma* (Rifkin et al., 2010) or the local *SECAP* (2021, updated in 2023), proposed techno and isomorphic solutions without any contextualisation and rooting of the strategies within local actors and innovative social practices (Nessi, 2018; De Pascali and Reginaldi, 2016). The result is evident: the energy consumption in the building and mobility sectors still plays a relevant role in carbon emissions;⁵ the construction of REN plants is weak,⁶ the application of energy efficiency measures often fails,⁷ and the house discomfort is growing with a high number of people suffering energy poverty condition.⁸

This critical framework underlines the urgency to overcome the spatial blindness of transition by rethinking tools that do not contemplate a standard or a mere technocratic approach but also integrate alternatives centred on local context and on space and its design. These tools do not constitute a clear picture yet and thus require innovative research paths. Building on the results of some research activities in the case study of Rome, the paper aims to explore spatial designs and urban planning strategies to figure out possible pathways for energy transitions by adopting a place-based perspective to integrate the current eco-modernist vision. The research question posed is thus: which tools and approaches enable the spatial design of place-based energy transition?

To address this question, the paper is structured as follows. The next section “Collecting theoretical references for a place-based energy design” establishes a theoretical framework

⁵ In the 2019, the emission amount around 8.410.000.000 tCO₂e; one third is in the mobility sector (around 2.930.000 tCO₂e). Source: Piano Clima Roma Capitale, 2023.

⁶ Within the city limits (1.285 km²), only 195 MW are available from 17.000 installations. Few of these are integrated into buildings, for example, only 1% of condominiums have photovoltaic systems. Source: Piano Clima Roma Capitale, 2023

⁷ Today 65,5% of the total building stock is certified according to the EU Energy Performance Certificate in classes F and G, the lowest. Source: Piano Clima Roma Capitale, 2023

⁸ In 2023, the local population in conditions of energy poverty exceeds 100.000 units (Asdrubali et. al., 2023).

based on a heterogeneous corpus of literature to bring together little-known and more radical energy paradigms with research on space and experiments in architectural and urban design. The third section, “Ostiense a place-based lab”, traced a research horizon and reported design strategies declined in the case study, following an introduction and problematisation of the context and the description of some actions from ongoing European JPI-funded research entitled PEDFORALL⁹. Each action tests one of the design strategies that emerged in the theoretical framework, tracing possible lines of research and design and discussing the idea of a place-based energy transition. The final section “Work in Progress: first Consideration and Future Developments” makes a recap of the consideration of the case study, merging theoretical reflections, design proposal and next research steps.

Collecting theoretical references for a place-based energy design

Overcoming the socio-spatial blindness of energy could mean a radical reinterpretation of the transition paradigms by questioning the premises instead of the assumptions. In this sense, it is useful to look at the transition paradigms defined as “radical” or “deep ecological” that advocate for a shift through a political-institutional revolution that challenges the assumptions of the energy system (Puttilli, 2014). These perspectives promote a co-evolution of the communities in the ecosystems while breaking away from contemporary development models in favour of reducing environmental pressures and fostering new social relations based on solidarity and sobriety. From this debate emerges the possibility of integrating the techno-economic concept of “efficiency” with the more socio-spatial of “sufficiency”. If theoretically applied to energy, sufficiency reduces “the problem” of consumption to its roots, eliminating or reducing some energy needs; in other words, i.e. reduces waste energy by consuming just “enough” (Burke, 2020). More precisely, energy sufficiency means that some behaviours and practices could reduce the need for some energy demands (Arrobbio, 2023) and call to the gesture of care where social engagement plays a fundamental and active role (Hertweck et. al, 2023).

The practices of energy sufficiency -per se- are quite explored and widely promoted: for example, the elimination of non-essential domestic appliances, the shading systems to reduce air conditioning use, and the car/ride-sharing systems to reduce individual consumption.¹⁰ Most of these solutions are based on deliberate and voluntary actions of individuals and mostly depend on personal cultural position (Sorrel et al., 2020), which is why sufficiency is still

⁹ The project involves an action-oriented network of PED and neighbourhood stakeholders in Belgium, Italy, and Turkey, who will apply a common co-design methodology to define a set of energy, policy, regulatory, governance, social, spatial, and design strategies for the implementation of Positive Energy District models. Three are the case study: Cultureghem in Bruxelles, Kartal in Istanbul. The Italian case study is in the neighbourhood of Ostiense and is led by the Architecture Department of Roma Tre University in collaboration with the Department of Law of the same university, the LUISS University, the Municipality of Municipio VIII.

¹⁰ An interesting example of sufficiency practices is reported in the guidelines of NégaWatt (2022) to promote energy sufficiency (referred to as sobriété) in France. Link to: <https://negawatt.org/The-negaWatt-2050-energy-scenario> (February, 2024)

considered an abstract paradigm. The factors to consider for enabling sufficiency practices encompass the complexity of the socio-economic dimension (work, age, education, etc.) as well as aspects more linked to the physical space. This latter aspect seems particularly interesting for the question raised in this paper: in fact, a way to give concreteness may be to understand how to create physical conditions to facilitate and replicate sufficient actions in specific contexts. For example, it is not enough to say to people “use the bike instead of a car”, but it is necessary to create spatial infrastructures that permit and encourage the use of a bike, such as cycle paths, widespread bike sharing, bike shelters, etc. In this sense, architectural and urban design expertise should converge to treat space as a continuum, shaped to accommodate configurations that enable social practices that reduce energy demand.

As a planning and design paradigm, reflections on sufficiency may tease the attention of architects and urban planners with the concepts of “taking care of the existing” producing design solutions and promoting narratives that do not waste or replace, but work with minimal gesture in the building heritage (Hertweck and Miessen, 2023). This paradigm goes beyond the just technofix of buildings, to rethink a radical mix of functions aiming to create a synergy between energy and other territorial systems and to optimise consumption through shared actions in spaces and with shared devices. Examples in this sense are the use of condominium laundries or bike/car sharing systems to reduce individual consumption or increase the quality of proximity daily-life open spaces to optimise uses and social practices as experimented in planning programmes such as “Superillas” in Barcelona; or the “Ville du quart d’heur” in Paris. Taking care of the existence means also saving the “embedded energy”, preserving, counting, and recycling the accumulation of the energies used for the construction, maintenance and transformation of architectures and spatial configurations (Viganò et al., 2015). Work with the embedded energy led to reparation and maintenance gestures (Denis and Pontille, 2019), reversing the capitalist imperatives of innovation-growth-progress that produce consumption, overuse, and squander into an idea that not everything is replaceable (Hertweck et al., 2023), not even with the most advanced technology. That involves rethinking buildings and open spaces as neutral and never-finished structures ensuring characteristics of flexibility and longevity, contrasting approaches of “deep rewriting” -often translated as demolition and reconstruction- accepting the existing and the idea to care for it over time.

Another spatial declination of sufficiency prompts a reconsideration of “the way we use energy in our daily-life spaces”, redefining and understanding our domestic energy landscape. This is not an easy task, the existing energy apparatuses (from a big power plant to the smallest appliance) are still “black boxes” where is not clear how they are made of and how they work (Denis and David, 2019). This is the result of a long process of detachment from the localised nexus of energy, which today is re-establishing connections with living communities (Pasqualetti and Stremke, 2017). Enhancing this nexus means deepening a context with place-based energy practices founded on public and shared interest within self and shared

responsibility, all aspect that calls for social innovation (Bragaglia, 2021). Inspiring examples in this sense are the experiences of self-build and self-maintenance of domestic spaces and devices that make inhabitants aware and conscious of their energy consumption system, independent from the supply of materials and services, and capable of producing intelligent solutions tailored to their own needs and mindful of the resources employed (Hertweck and Miessen, 2023).

Thinking about “intelligent” and self-tailored energy solutions induces an awareness of social practices and the spatial design we inhabit. As suggested by Elisabeth Shove (2007), the design of everyday life influences our performances in spaces and the constellations of products and practices co-evolving in cycles of production, consumption, and innovation. Our energy performances are particularly linked to daily comfort perception that to guarantee indoor and outdoor standards in terms of lighting, cooling, heating, and ventilation, a huge amount of energy is consumed. Interpreting comfort from a sufficiency perspective means rethinking the goals of achieving “standards” just by equipping spaces and architectures with homologated technological solutions such as artificially illuminating dark spaces, cooling warm environments with appliances, etc. As the work of Barber (2020) shows, the imposition of a universal technological standardisation of comfort has reduced and trivialised the relationship between the artefacts and the context in which they are located, entrusting mediation to mechanical means or relying on fossil fuels. Design explorations, as those of Victor and Aladar Olgyay, Glenn Murcutt, and Lacaton and Vassal, establish a close relationship with the external atmospheric and climatic conditions of the site to achieve a high level of climatic comfort with a minimum use of artificial air conditioning, ventilation, or heating devices. This line of research, better known as bioclimatic architecture, is once again attracting attention, and a set of solutions that make an economy of means is seen as one that can help to rearticulate the architectural project (Rahm, 2023a; Rahm, 2023b), also inspiring people to innovative solutions that reduce electrical and thermal dependency, even reducing the energy poverty status. At the urban scale, the sufficiency approach to comfort is informing many research and projects, particularly those dealing with the UHI effect. For example, the use of “cool material techniques” to reconfigure permeable paving with light-coloured asphalt or similar to reduce the albedo index (APUR, 2020); or the transformation of existing roofs to host PV panels or gardens to improve the self-consumption of energy and passively insulate buildings and reduce surface overheating (Guida, 2022; Toboso et al., 2023).

From these reference collections emerge at least three possible spatial strategies for a place-based design of energy transition. The first is described by the concept of “taking care of the existing” which forces working with and on the existing urban configuration and not on a “tabula rasa”, acting on the quality of spaces and on the sharing of practices and devices to avoid the proliferation of individual consumption, and with gestures of repair to adapt the existing to new uses and configurations and planning its maintenance. The second strategy

focuses intensely on learning from social practices where the relationship between energy devices, energy metabolisms and energy behaviours is evident, and its design in domestic and urban spaces led to more intelligent and sensible consumption. The last strategy explores the management of comfort for less use of energy with the design of bioclimatic architecture and urban spaces. Each strategy, although not exhaustive and reinterpretable, has guided some test actions in the case study, which will be reported in the next paragraph.

Ostiense: A Place-Based Lab

Returning to the research question, namely, with what tools and approaches is it possible to spatially design the transition in defined contexts, and to test the design strategies for a place-based energy transition, it is necessary to draw the boundaries of a specific case study. Within the city of Rome, the choice fell on the Ostiense neighbourhood, a paradigmatic case due to its historical, urban and energy characteristics. The neighbourhood is recognised as Rome's historic energy district still characterised today by the presence of old energy infrastructures, including the former Italgas area (12 hectares with an iconic 90-meter-high gasometer) which today hosts a technological hub for new energies,¹¹ and the Montemartini thermoelectric power plant, which now houses an archaeological museum. From an urban planning perspective, the neighbourhood represents a consolidated and stratified urban pattern, in large part historical, characterised also by the presence of a university district and large former industrial areas undergoing regeneration, both characteristics of an interesting urban transformation area. The Ostiense energy system shows a great imbalance between consumption and production: an average of 150 MWh is consumed monthly, while the installed capacity, including the existing renewable energy installations, is only 0,4 MWp. Here, a significant weight of consumption is linked to the specific spatial-environmental phenomenon of UHIs. Ostiense is one of the hottest parts of Rome in summer, especially at nighttime when the temperature can rise to +3°C compared to the average in Rome (Pone, 2023). This condition leads to an impressive use of artificial air conditioning, with a +10% increase in electricity demand compared to the monthly average in Rome (ARETI, 2021). Many studies, such as the ones by Cattaneo (2023), show that the UHIs are strongly influenced by given topographic conditions such as the large presence of asphalted surfaces, the scarce availability of permeable soils, the lack of vegetation, and the massive use of cars.

¹¹ The ROAD -Rome Advanced District is a network of enterprises involved in innovative technological development. More detail available at the link: <https://www.roadlab.tech/it> (September 2024).

Figure 2: The “asphalt landscapes” of Rome. Oversized road sections, parking lots, asphalted courtyards and squares cover large areas of the city, absorbing a lot of heat and generating the Urban Heat Island phenomenon. (Via Ostiense-Rome. Credits: Fabrizio D’Angelo, 2023).

Rome metropolitan area

Ostiense district

1_Piramide; 2_Porto Fluviale; 3_Ex Italgas; 4_Ex Mercati Generali; 5_University; 6_Parc; 7_St. Paul's Basilica; 8_School distric

Figure 3: Ostiense location within the city of Rome (credits: Fabrizio D’Angelo, 2024).

Figure 4: The historical and consolidated city. The estimated energy efficiency heritage of Ostiense, where just a dozen buildings (the greener ones) were built after the first Italian law on consumption control, so the larger part of the buildings is supposed to be in a deficit of energy efficiency. (credits: Fabrizio D'Angelo, 2023).

The local consumption system is also influenced by both the quality of the buildings and the social component of the tenants. The neighbourhood largely consists of buildings constructed between the early 20th century and the 1970s, predating the first energy efficiency law in 1976. Few are the retrofitting operations on a very old and highly fragmented property, often complicated by superimposed structures and unregulated interventions. Even rarer are the housing units with energy-efficient solutions, often resulting from demolition and reconstruction projects or simple new construction on the few empty lots. The same housing units are often rented out, sometimes for very short periods, especially for the large number of students living in the neighbourhood (Ostiense is consolidating as one of the university districts of Rome). This condition hinders the possibility for residents and tenants to directly intervene in their energy systems. Additionally, it should be noted that there are users in energy poverty conditions and squats with hundreds of users whose comfort conditions require urgent attention.¹²

The rich complexity of the context defines the ideal characteristics for experimenting and testing the strategies outlined for a place-based energy transition. These tests are currently carried out in three PEDFORALL research actions that, although following different work packages and deliverables,¹³ contribute to the development of an integrated design strategy.

¹² In the neighbourhood there is a historical squatter building named “Porto Fluviale” which is under retrofit renovation by a public fund. The building, since 2003, is inhabited by 56 households from 13 different nations. The project includes insulation systems and the creation of a photovoltaic system for self-consumption. More information at (March 2024)

¹³ The different actions described are part of ongoing work packages: the first is part of WP4 “Strategies for a Neighbourhood in Transition”; the second is part of WP5 “Living Lab”, and the third one is linked to research-related training projects.

Each of these actions is tailored to one of the strategies identified in section 2, namely: the care of the existing, the energy behaviours and practices, and the bioclimatic design.

Figure 5: Energy devices exposure. Over the years, the buildings in the neighbourhood, lacking energy efficiency solutions, have been equipped with devices to mitigate living comfort, such as air conditioners, boilers, curtains, and ventilation systems (via Negri - Ostiense. Credits: Fabrizio D'Angelo, 2023).

As for the care of the existing, the first research action codesign strategies to apply the principles of a PED model to existing urban patterns. Here, a new analytical tool is needed to handle the complexity between lack of space, stratified build heritage, heterogeneous social components and fragmented regulatory frameworks. The new tool created and tested is entitled “Atlas of strategies” a matrix that crosses three different perspectives, each requiring different expertise. The three perspectives analyse the context, deepening the social, governance and spatial dimensions; the regulatory and policy system; and the energy and technological status.¹⁴ Planning an ongoing transformation means considering also the time evolution and the development of different processes. For this reason, each perspective understands and orders the socio-spatial energy issues in three steps starting from the existing energy niches (e.g. the innovative actions of a local Renewable Energy Community¹⁵; or the local regulatory framework for the retrofitting of squatters building); the operating of the existing energy system (grid, presence of electrical cabins), and characteristics of the urban landscape. The elements collected from this cross-analysis are then analysed by success factors, challenges, and barriers, underlining the strong interconnection with the existing

¹⁴ The PEDFORALL research group merge different expertise: the department of Architecture of Roma Tre University and the Vrije Universiteit Brussel for issues linked to spatial design and governance system; the Istanbul Technical University for technological issues; the Department of Law of Roma Tre University and the Luiss University for regulatory and policies framework.

¹⁵ In Ostiense is being set up a Solidarity Energy Community that share public roofs to produce photovoltaic energy distributed then to energy-poverty users. For more details follow the link: <https://www.cermunicipio8.it/chi-siamo/> (September 2024).

context. For example, it emerges a lack of large, unified spaces to install self-production energy systems but the presence of many public buildings (e.g. university buildings), which have large rooftops and are spread throughout the neighbourhood, can support the shared use of energy community serving the public interest. Or again, the presence of a museum in a former power plant could enhance spaces for energy-educational and awareness programs. These examples, along with others, have contributed to defining design strategies tailored for the Ostiense context, expressed by visuals and shared with local stakeholders.

As for the behaviour and practices perspective, the second research action is entitled “Paesaggio Elettro-Domestico”, which in English sounds like an “Electro-Domestic” Landscape. In the context of PEDFORALL living labs, the relationship between energy devices, energy metabolisms and energy behaviours in domestic and urban dimensions has been explored. The action consists of interacting interviews with a selected group of inhabitants, chosen by different social, economic and professional statuses, paying attention also to the housing architectural conditions such as exposition, square meters, number of floors, year of construction, etc. With tenants are testing different kinds of representation and analysis. As a first step, using maquettes that reproduce the space of the interviewee's apartment, residents are asked to list and place all appliances and, in doing so, indicate their efficiency level (how old they are) and usage intensity. Based on a colour-coding system, each device is then classified according to its consumption intensity. This first step offers a form of spatialisation and qualification of domestic energy consumption. The second step focuses on the spatialisation of energy practices. Still using the maquettes, residents are asked to describe the practices they undertake to achieve or maintain indoor comfort and to indicate where and with which devices these practices occur. In this second step, forms are provided to spatialise energy practices and spatial conditions, particularly the building envelope and various technological systems. The result is a survey of how domestic spaces evolve regarding electrical appliances and, through the direct involvement of inhabitants, an awareness of everything that consumes energy and the spatial influence of energy behaviours. For example, it emerged that some energy consumptions are concentrated not only in specific rooms but also in spaces defined by comfort conditions (near a window, at a table, or in a well-ventilated spot); or that the availability of accessible outdoor spaces reduces the use of certain appliances (clotheslines instead of dryer machines) or decreases the need for artificial lighting. Even more interesting insights emerged from the analysis of energy practices to thermal comfort. In environments that are not fully or permanently artificially climate-controlled, people interact with space in search of thermal balance, often adopting creative and effective spatial solutions. For instance, it has been observed that in apartments with only one air-conditioned room, during the hot months, this space is repurposed to accommodate multiple activities, from sleeping to working and leisure. In these cases, the space is adapted to accommodate the rhythms of different functions coexisting within the same area. Other interesting aspects include the awareness

that has developed around the domestic experience, such as thermal conditions or convection. This is evident in DIY design solutions, for example, moving sofas and beds away from sun-exposed warm walls, using rugs to mitigate cold drafts in winter, and strategically opening doors and windows to create airflow.

Figure 6: “Electro-domestic” landscape. Moment of the workshops with inhabitants to understand and spatialise energy consumption and behaviours. (Credits: Fabrizio D’Angelo, 2024).

Finally, the bioclimatic perspective was implemented through *the* “Urban Frigidarium”, a program of different on-site training projects which aims to test the transformation of public spaces with bioclimatic strategies. The first workshop is entitled “Marciapiede Fresco”¹⁶, which in English could be translated as “fresh sidewalk”. The workshop was a one-day open-air building site, focused on the transformation of a large asphalted surface in front of a school. The operation was promoted by PEDFORALL local consortium¹⁷ and involved local actors and students at a university laboratory in urbanism. During a thermolaser survey to monitor the effects of UHI, it emerged that many urban soils with existing large asphalt surfaces (parking lots, streets, yards) absorb significant amounts of heat. As a result, it emerged that the UHI affects local energy consumption with intense use of comfort appliances (air conditioners, electrical fans, and dehumidifiers) that increase the 22% electricity consumption (Asdrubali et al. 2022). Among the spaces monitored, a big sidewalk in front of a school appeared as the hottest surface of the surroundings. Starting from design references of bioclimatic design,

¹⁶ The workshop was part of the university lab of “Progettazione dello Spazio Urbano-LMPU” involving the researchers Fabrizio D’Angelo, Margherita Ermani, Ilaria Maurelli, Maria Pone, Marco Ranzato. The students involved from Roma Tre University- Department of Architecture are: Ait Baady Imane, Bevilacqua Marta, Comanducci Martina, Consiglio Tommaso, Cucciniello Matteo, D’Almeida Vitoria D’Ambrosio Anna, De Mari Laura, De Rosa Sarah, Del Gizzo Alisee, D’Emilio Chiara, Di Cesare Chiara, Di Dio Federico, Fabbri Edoardo, Fernandez Covadonga, Filoni Francesco, Fournier Emilie, Hesse Justine, Lemme Francesco, Marinangeli Riccardo, Marzo Alberto, Matehau Rehia, Mika Jiri, Brustolon Leonardo, Panico Anna, Ruiz Cobosm Elena Maria, Salzano Barbara Judith.

¹⁷The local consortium is made by Roma Tre University and the local municipality Municipio VIII. The initiative was supported by the “Dipartimento Politiche Sociali e Salute, Roma Capitale - Municipio VIII” and sponsored by “SportLab” association.

specifically the use of Cool Materials, almost 100 kg of white paint was used to recover approximately 250 square meters of the asphalted surface. Due to the proximity to a school, the painted areas also featured lettering about rising temperature and UHI effect. The action was particularly interesting for the social interaction it fostered. The white sidewalk attracted the attention of many residents and passers-by who crossed the transformed space getting in touch with the meaning of the workshop. The exchange between “workers” and citizens provided an opportunity to test the acceptability of the intervention and discuss and disseminate themes related to energy consumption mitigation.

Figure 6: “Marciapiede Fresco”, the open construction site to test the Cool Materials technique. (Largo da Vinci-Rome, credits: Fabrizio D’Angelo, 2023).

Work in Progress: first Consideration and Future Developments

The case study experiences represent a new research approach that mixes different methodologies, outputs and tools. The neighbourhood was considered not just in terms of its techno-energetic potentialities (e.g. numbers of PV installable on roofs, amount of energy reduced in energy class upgrade), neither standardised scenario building approach was applied based on spatial-neutral common collection of good practices (e.g. a list of general objectives as those defined in SECAP plans). This territorial lens, instead, focused on closely observing the case study first, starting from its socio-spatial, technological, and legal conditions, and only in a second phase defining a possible vision of transition. This perspective guides the first action that, using a double lens, crosses socio-spatial and energy considerations in the context, providing a deep and critical analysis of the case study, highlighting the real needs and objectives of the transition and avoiding applying ready-made programs. At the same time, the threshold analysis by energy niches, energy context and urban landscape, built during the “Atlas of strategies”, gives a more complex image of the possible

declination of the transition, emphasising possible success but also challenges. Start by planning an urban energy transition from the socio-spatial dimension, and not just by adapting an energy model, makes a difference in the quality and feasibility of the interventions. For example, this first action has brought to light that the application of energy efficiency models in existing buildings is difficult due to constraints related to historical heritage, as well as the fragmentation of property ownership and the different economic statuses of the inhabitants. At the same time, this type of analysis also highlights possible solutions. By valuing the preservation of existing structures, a careful study and description of the spaces and social dynamics of the neighbourhood reveals, for example, how the presence of numerous university buildings, with large and public roofs, can support the installation of energy production systems to be shared within an Energy Community.

This methodological tool is certainly applicable to any context; however, the results provide, each time, different and place-based urban design strategies. Observing the socio-spatial complexities of what already exists enhances the concept of "taking care of the existence," aiming to maximise the value of present spatial capital while preserving the embedded energy. These strategies, though seemingly obvious when intervening in a consolidated urban context, are still slow to be fully integrated into the political and planning visions for cities. Certainly, part of this resistance is driven by the many technological projects that attract capital and expertise in the urban transformation processes. On the other hand, however, there is still not enough design culture to rethink the energy transition of consolidated urban areas in an alternative way. The tested tool is merely a first attempt to offer concrete support and encouragement to restart from the existing, both spatial and social, to carefully and appropriately tailor a new urban energy system.

While a place-based analysis of the context can provide solid support for formulating design strategies, a large part of the energy system remains uncontrolled and unknown. The scale of consumption is still largely abstract, and, more importantly, actions to manage it are often limited to technological improvements. The construction of the "Electro-domestic landscapes" of the case study seeks to fill the knowledge gap related to energy behaviours and their relationship with space. "Electro-domestic landscape" serves as a test-lab to understand and then visualise the physical dimension of spatial design in social behaviours with relation to energy consumption. Working with residents in their domestic spaces creates the opportunity to build an interactive design process that moves through understanding, hypothesis formulation, and testing with the direct stakeholders. Using design tools, such as the maquettes, facilitates the spatialisation of energy behaviours and the interaction with the interviewer who is also a user and inhabitant. All the information collected -as the DIY solution and the use of artefacts or spaces to do things instead of using electrical appliances- are signs of a possible new culture of energy-sufficient design. The same ideas could be extended to the urban dimension, understanding how open and public spaces, infrastructures, workplaces,

and leisure landscapes shape our energy behaviours and how they could reduce energy consumption through a different configuration or function. This echoes some urban transformation paradigms, such as the “15-minute city”, which, however, are primarily focused on mobility. By starting from the energy dimension, these same paradigms can be enriched and deepened, providing a more comprehensive vision of socio-ecological transition. Exploring the bodily and social dimensions of energy habits also prompts a reflection on thermal comfort. “Marciapiede Fresco” and the other actions of “Frigidario Urbano”, are conceived as instant construction sites to test, simulate, and design potential transformations in existing urban patterns. Bioclimatic solutions such as the use of Cool Materials are quite well known in the urban design culture, although are lacking, again, experimentations in consolidated, stratified, and historic urban contexts. The operations carried out do not offer certain, ready-to-use, and lasting solutions, with the risk of generating scarce acceptability and difficult replications. However, they provide a space for temporary experimentation that simulates, measures and adjusts configurations and devices in search of the best-suited formula for a specific site. In “Marciapiede Fresco” a blank white surface was left without any design, and a film of Cool Material was available for monitoring temperature and paint wear.

Observations made in the following months showed its effectiveness in terms of climate mitigation, with an average asphalt temperature decrease of -10°C . However, some critical issues were noted, such as the paint's durability near vegetation and the blinding effect of the white colour reported by some residents. These construction sites are essentially attempting to disseminate a simulation that is useful both in design terms -only by testing on a real scale can the strengths and weaknesses of the action be identified- and as learning spaces. Getting back to the research questions, all the actions presented above, although separately implemented, contribute to the search and the definition of a range of tools and approaches for a place-based energy transition in consolidated urban contexts. The premise of working with existing configurations opens a field of study and experimentation that is far from being fully explored but is still urgent given the urban structure of many European cities and the planning paradigms no longer oriented toward expansion but toward rewriting. This represents a different way of observing cities, as well as a different foundation for making planning choices related to energy. The strategies themselves are based not only on careful contextual analysis but also on interaction with energy behaviours, breaking through the veil that has long covered the social dimension of energy. This highlights that not only can technological performance mitigate consumption, but also the space in which it occurs. Finally, some proposed strategies, much like in a scientific laboratory, have been tested in physical space. These simulations support the idea that innovation in the energy transition must not only arise from total-tech experimentation but should also occur within the dimension of spatial design.

The considerations, the concepts adopted, and the references used reaffirm the interest in advancing the paradigm of energy sufficiency. However, this does not imply a total rejection of other energy visions but rather a harmonious integration. Technological innovation and its application in architecture and urban planning -as proposed in the eco-modernist visions of EU policies- are certainly valid and necessary, and the energy sufficiency dimension still retains a certain critical and naive dimension. Nevertheless, it is enriching and sometimes essential to complement more established pathways with alternative experiences to contribute to a stronger idea of place-based energy transition.

The strategies proposed are not yet mature enough to represent a solution, but they serve as alternative points of observation to rethink the role of energy transition in urban areas. Therefore, this contribution aims to provide suggestions, entry points, and references to fuel the debate. PEDFORALL is, and will continue to be, engaged in developing further strategies: additional bioclimatic experiments on public space are underway (a new cooling device using water is being implemented in a public square), other workshops for the electro-domestic landscape are taking place (currently involving three new apartments), and the strategies outlined in the atlas will soon be shared in a publication. Hopefully, the reflections presented here will align with the new research results, stimulating a work that will find other opportunities for dissemination. Similarly, the thoughts and strategies produced will stimulate other works to enrich the debate on place-based energy transitions.

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Conflict of interest

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